

ISOLATION AND EVALUATION OF ANTIOXIDANT AND ANTIBACTERIAL
ACTIVITIES OF FUCOIDAN RICH EXTRACT (FRE) FROM INDIAN BROWN
SEAWEED, *Sargassum wightii*

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ABSTRACT

Brown seaweed, *Sargassum* spp. has been traditionally used in the Chinese medicine as a food ingredient for the treatment of Scrofula, goiter, tumor, edema, testicular pain and swelling. Now-a-days isolation of fucoidan, a bioactive compound present in this brown seaweed is getting increasing interest because of its multifunction including antibacterial and antioxidant activity. A simple alcohol-water method was used for the extraction of fucoidan from Indian brown seaweed *Sargassum wightii*. The crude fucoidan yield was 5.5% of dry weight of seaweed and the L-fucose content was 31.61mg/g dried seaweed powder. Three antioxidant activity screening assays such as diphenylpicrylhydrazyl (DPPH) scavenging activity, ferric reducing antioxidant power assay (FRAP) and total phenolic assays (TPA) were selected to identify the antioxidant activity of fucoidan rich extract (FRE). The antioxidant activity of FRE exhibited a linear relationship, $y = 9.01x + 19.18$; $R^2 = 0.97$, $y = 20.09x + 25.29$; $R^2 = 0.98$ and $y = 13.46x - 11.61$; $R^2 = 0.99$ respectively for DPPH, FRAP and TPA. The antibacterial activity was estimated by minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) and minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC). The FRE also inhibited the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Micrococcus luteus* and *Aeromonas hydrophila* at MIC of 62.5, 125.0 and 62.5 μ l/ml, respectively. Hence, *Sargassum wightii* possesses antibacterial activity against gram positive and gram negative pathogens and contains good antioxidant activity as well.

KEYWORDS: Fucoidan, seaweed, antioxidant, polysaccharide, FRE, DPPH, FRAP, Total phenolic content, MIC, MBC.

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INTRODUCTION

Brown seaweeds have been traditionally used in the Chinese medicine as a food ingredient. The medicinal benefits are mainly due to the presence of fucoidan. The term fucoidan is generally used to describe the family of polysaccharides containing L-fucose as one of the major monosaccharides, which are highly sulphated and

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contains varying amounts of glucuronic acid and xylose. Fucoidan is a high-molecular weight (about 20000 Da) water soluble dietary fibre or polysaccharide. The sulphated fucoidan is located in the intercellular tissue and most strikingly in droplets that exude from the surface of the fronds from the brown seaweeds (Doner & Whistler, 1973). Two different forms of fucoidan are recognized from seaweeds; one is U-fucoidan composed of over 95% sulfated esters of L-fucose and the other one is F-fucoidan containing approximately 20% glucuronic acid in their composition. The structures of fucoidans from different brown algae vary from species to species sometimes even different parts of algae (Chevolotet *et al.*, 1999).

Fucoidans have several biochemical properties. Biological activities of fucoidans occur mainly due to their high degree of sulfation, although these activities possibly depend on fine structural peculiarities and molecular weight (Nagumo *et al.*, 1996). Fucoidans are known to have antitumour, anticancer, anticoagulant, antimetastatic, fibrinolytic, antiviral, antibacterial and antioxidant properties (Maruyama *et al.*, 1987). Antioxidant and antibacterial activity of fucoidan is related to its molecular weight and sulfate content. The correlation between the sulfate content and scavenging superoxide radical ability was positive, the ratio of sulfate content/fucose was an effective indicator to antioxidant activity of the samples (Wang *et al.*, 2008).

Chotigeat *et al.* (2004) noted that the oral administration of *Sargassum polycystum* crude fucoidan (CF) inhibited the growth of *Vibrio harveyi*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* at minimal inhibition concentrations. Huang *et al.* (2006) reported that oral administration of *Sargassum fusiforme* polysaccharide extracts effectively improved vibriosis resistance in *Fennero penaeus chinensis*. According to Traifalgar *et al.* (2010) juveniles of *Marsupenaeus japonicas* fed with diets supplemented with *Undaria pinnatifida* fucoidan had potential serum antibacterial effect against *Vibrio harveyi*.

The structural complexity and chemical composition of algal fucoidan may vary depending on the methods of extraction and location (Grauffel *et al.*, 1989). Thus, each new fucoidan isolated from different algal species exhibit distinct structured compound with unique potential in bioactivity. Several methods were used to extract fucoidan from different species from various geographical location of world (Wang & Zhae, 1985; Colleic *et al.*, 1994; Dietrich *et al.*, 1995; Hoshino *et al.*, 1998; Pereira *et al.*, 1999 and Chotigeat *et al.*, 2004). But there is not much information available for the isolation of fucoidan from Indian seaweeds except the pioneer work was done by Velayutham & Jayachandran (1991).

Though the antioxidant and antibacterial activities were done earlier in fucoidan from different algae but there is no work has been done from Indian brown seaweed, *Sargassum wightii*. Hence, the present study was focused on the isolation of fucoidan rich extract (FRE) by a simple least cost alcohol water method and furthers its antioxidant and antibacterial activities from *S. wightii*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Seaweed collection and sample preparation

For this study Indian brown sea weed, *Sargassum wightii* were collected from Mandapam, Ramanathapuram district at Tamil Nadu southern coast of India. Fresh brown sea weed samples were collected from the sea with

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a help of fisherman. *Sargassum wightii* specimens were sorted out, which was the major portion of harvested seaweeds.

Freshly collected matured, disease free and healthy brown seaweed, *Sargassum wightii* was thoroughly washed in freshwater to remove dirt and other extraneous materials adhering to them and shade dried for about three days. The shade dried *Sargassum wightii* were pulverised to fine powder. One kilogram fresh seaweed yields approximately 100g dried powder.

Fucoidan rich extract preparation (alcohol – water method)

The dry seaweed powder of 100 gram was taken into an appropriate sized vessel to which 1L of 85% ethanol was added, followed by stirring with a magnetic stirrer (REMI) for 12 hrs. The alcohol was decanted and washed with acetone. It was centrifuged at 18000 rpm using REMI centrifuge for 10 min and the supernatant was decanted. The residual seaweed was dried at room temperature at least to remove the acetone completely. Further, the dried residue was added with 700 ml distilled water and stirred for 1hr at 65°C. The hot mixture (70°C) was filtered and the filtrate was collected. The residue was re-extracted with 350 ml of distilled water as done before and filtered again. Both extracts were mixed together and centrifuged at 18000 rpm for 10min. The supernatant was collected and 1% CaCl₂ was added by vigorous mixing, which was stored at 4°C for overnight to precipitate the alginic acid as a calcium salt of alginate. Next day morning, precipitated mixture was centrifuged and the brown colour pellet was removed by leaving the same colour aliquot. This supernatant was crude fucoidan extract. The excess water content was removed by simple evaporation method at 60°C in water bath. The crude fucoidan was purified by using dialysis membrane. This FRE was used for the evaluation of antioxidant and antibacterial properties.

Quantification of fucoidan from FRE:

Fucoidan content was estimated in terms of L-fucose content of the extract. The L-fucose content was analysed by following the method of Dubois *et al.* (1956). Two millilitre of FRE was pipetted into calorimetric tube and 50 µl of 80% phenol was added. Then 5 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid was added rapidly, the stream of acid being directed against the liquid surface rather than against the side of the test tube to ensure proper mixing. The tube was allowed to stand for 10 min, followed by shaking and placed for 20 min in water bath at 37°C. The absorbance of the characteristic yellow-orange was measured at 480 nm. The amount of fucoidan was calculated according to Doner & Whisler (1973) whereby 1 µg of fucoidan is equivalent to 1.75x fucose (µg).

$$\text{Fucoidan } (\mu\text{g/ml}) = 1.75 \times \text{fucose } (\mu\text{g/ml})$$

Methods for screening antioxidant properties

Estimation of DPPH (2,2-Diphenyl-1-Picrylhydrozyl)

The DPPH (2, 2 – Diphenyl -1-Picrylhydrozyl) radical is deep purple in color. The purple chromogen radical is reduced by antioxidant / reducing compound to the corresponding pale yellow hydrazine. The fucoidan sample with different volumes with range from 25µl to 150 µl was taken and 2 ml of methanolic DPPH 0.06

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M was added. Then it was mixed well and kept at dark room for 30 min. The OD value was measured at 517nm in spectrophotometer.

Estimation of total phenolic content

Total phenolic content in the FRE was estimated by the method of Singleton & Rossy (1965). Thirty micro-litre of FRE was taken in a test tube and the volume was made up to 3 ml with the distilled water. 0.5 ml of Folin-ciocalteau reagent was added to the test tube. After 3 minutes, 2 ml of 20% sodium carbonate was added and mixed well. The tubes were then placed in boiling water exactly for 1 min, cooled and the absorbance was measured using spectrophotometer at 650 nm against a reagent blank. A standard curve was prepared for different concentration of the working standard. The content of the phenols in the test samples were found out from the standard curve and the results were expressed as mg phenols/100g sample.

Ferric reducing antioxidant power assay (FRAP)

The FRAP assay was carried out according to the procedure of Benzie (1997) with some modifications. The FRAP reagent was prepared fresh daily and was warmed to 37 °C in a water bath prior to use. 50µl of sample was added to 1.5 ml of the FRAP reagent. The absorbance of the reaction mixture was then recorded at 593 nm after 4 min. The standard curve was prepared using iron (II) sulfate solution (100–2000 µM), and the results were expressed as µ mol Fe (II)/g dry weight of plant material. All the measurements were taken in duplicate and the mean values were calculated.

Antibacterial assay

Gram positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Micrococcus luteus* and gram negative bacteria *Aeromonas hydrophila* were used in this assay. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of FRE was determined by Micro Broth Dilution method according to the National Committee for Clinical Laboratory Standard (NCCLS, 1999) guidelines using a 96 well plate. 100 µl of sterilized MHB (Mueller Hinton Broth) was added in each well of plate. Then, 100 µl of FRE was added and subsequently serial dilution was performed so that concentrations in the range of 1000µl/ml to 3.75µl/ml were obtained. 10 µl inoculums of each bacterium were added to all wells and incubated at ambient temperature for 24 hrs. A positive control (contain inoculums but no FRE) and a negative control (containing FRE but no inoculums) were included on each plates. The MIC was determined by quantitative tetrazolium based colorimetric method. In this 10 µl of 1% TTC (2,3,5-triphenyl tetrazolium chloride) was added to each well. Plates were kept at 30°C and the results were recorded. A colour change to pinkish red colour was taken as positive. The minimum bactericidal concentrations (MBC) were determined by first selecting wells that showed no growth during MIC determination. For this, a loopful from each well was sub cultured onto extracts free Mueller Hinton Agar plates and incubated for further 24 hrs 37°C. The lowest concentration at which there was no growth observed and noted as MBC.

Statistical analysis

The data were statistically analyzed by statistical package SPSS version 16.0 in which data were subjected to one way ANOVA and Duncan's multiple range tests was used to determine the significant differences between the means. Comparisons were made at the 5% probability level.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Quantification of fucoidan from FRE:

The dialysed FRE was quantified by measuring the L-fucose content which was multiplied by the factor 1.75 (Doner & Whisler, 1973). The L-fucose content was determined by colorimetric method and the quantity of L-fucose was 31.61 mg/g dried seaweed powder. Hence, the fucoidan content was 55 mg/g or 5.5 g/100 g dried seaweed powder. One ml of FRE was obtained from 2 g dry seaweed powder and 1 ml FRE contains 110 mg fucoidan.

Several methods were used to extract fucoidan from different species, such as *Dictyotamertensis*, *Padina gymnospora* and *Sargassu mvulgare* by Maxatase (Dietrich *et al.*, 1995), *Facusvesiculosus*, *Laminaria brasiliensis* and *Ascophyllum nodosum* by papain (Pereira *et al.*, 1999), *Sargassum horneri* by 10% TCA (Hoshino *et al.*, 1998) and *Sargassum horneri*, *Sargassum ilicifolium*, *Padinac analiculata* and *Sargassum polycystum* by HCl (Wang & Zhae, 1985; Velayutham & Jayachandran, 1991; Colleic *et al.*, 1994; Chotigeat *et al.*, 2004). The yield varied widely, depending on the method used and the seaweed species. The inexpensive and convenient alcohol-water method was used in this present study, which can be developed for the large scale preparation of fucoidan. In the present study, fucoidan content of *Sargassum wightii* was 5.5%. This is in agreement with Eluvakkal *et al.* (2010), Velayutham & Jayachandran (1991) and Wang & Zhae (1985), who reported that the fucoidan content from *Sargassum wightii*, *Sargassum ilicifolium* and *Sargassum horneri* was 7.15%, 4.2% and 3.9%, respectively.

Antioxidant properties of FRE:

There are several methods available for extracting the antioxidants from plant materials (organic solvent extraction, aqueous extraction etc). Considering the acceptability by an animal and possible solvent residue problem, aqueous extraction method was used in the present study. The antioxidant capacities of the plant extracts are largely dependent on the compositions of the extract and conditions of the test system (Li *et al.*, 2007). The antioxidant capacities are influenced by many factors that can't be fully described with one single method. Thus, three antioxidant activity screening assays were selected to take into account the various mechanisms of antioxidant action.

DPPH (2, 2 -Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) radical scavenging method

The radical scavenging capacity of the FRE with different concentrations was tested using the 'stable' free radical, DPPH. Table 1 shows the ability of each concentrations of fucoidan to scavenge DPPH radical and the scavenging values are represented as inhibition (%). The FRE exhibited varying degrees of scavenging capacities based on its concentration of fucoidan. The scavenging capacity increased with the increasing concentration of fucoidan. The antioxidant activity of FRE exhibited the linear relationship $y = 9.01x + 19.18$; $R^2 = 0.97$ for this method (Fig 1). The maximum concentration (16.5mg/ml) showed the highest radical scavenging effect (73.10±1.27%) and the least concentration (2.75 mg/ml) showed less scavenging effect (24.67 ±1.57%).

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DPPH is a free radical compound that has been widely used to determine the free radical scavenging capacity of various samples (Hatano *et al.*, 1988; Amarowicz *et al.*, 2004) because of its stability (in radical form), simplicity and fast assay (Bozin *et al.*, 2008). The higher concentration of FRE exhibited highest free radical scavenging activity. This suggested that greater total phenolic contents may be translated into increased DPPH free radical scavenging activity. According to Li *et al.* (2007) boiling could be the better choice for obtaining antioxidant rich material from plants which may be compared with the hot aqueous extraction method employed in the present experiment for fucoidan extraction.

Table 1: Antioxidant properties of FRE:

Concentrations (mg/ml)	DPPH (Inhibition %)	FRAP (μ mol Fe(II)/g dry wt)	Total phenolics(mg phenols/100g)
2.75	24.67 ^a $\pm$ 1.57	42.46 ^a $\pm$ 3.97	2.42 ^a $\pm$ 0.30
5.5	39.62 ^b $\pm$ 1.68	65.46 ^b $\pm$ 4.65	15.67 ^b $\pm$ 1.30
8.25	49.30 ^c $\pm$ 0.56	87.96 ^c $\pm$ 3.61	26.58 ^c $\pm$ 0.93
11	55.83 ^d $\pm$ 1.46	106.62 ^d $\pm$ 4.56	41.83 ^d $\pm$ 1.06
13.75	61.88 ^e $\pm$ 1.31	131.63 ^e $\pm$ 3.90	58.75 ^e $\pm$ 1.53
16.5	73.10 ^f $\pm$ 1.27	139.71 ^e $\pm$ 0.36	67.75 ^f $\pm$ 0.29
P value	0.001	0.001	0.001

Mean values in the same column with different superscript differ significantly (P<0.05). Data expressed as Mean $\pm$ SE, n=3

Fig 1: Inhibition % of FRE with different concentration analysed using DPPH radical scavenging method

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Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power Assay (FRAP)

FRAP values consistently increased with the increasing concentration of fucoidan up to the level of 13.75 mg/ml. The antioxidant activity of FRE exhibited the linear relationship $y = 20.09x + 25.29$; $R^2 = 0.98$ for this method. However, there was no significant difference ($P < 0.05$) between the concentration of 13.75 and 16.5 mg/ml level (Fig 2).

The highest value ($139.71 \pm 0.39 \mu \text{ mol Fe}^{2+}/\text{g}$) of FRAP was found at 16 mg/ml concentration of fucoidan. The antioxidant activities of phenolic compounds are mainly of redox properties, including free radical scavenging, hydrogen donating and singlet oxygen quenching (Mayachiew & Devahastin, 2008). Pulido *et al.* (2000) reported the reducing capacity of polyphenols as determined by the FRAP assay. This seems to depend on the degree of hydroxylation and extent of conjugation of the phenolic compounds.

Fig 2: FRAP values of FRE with different concentration analysed using FRAP assay

Total phenolic assay

Total phenolic of all the FRE with different concentrations were significantly different ($P < 0.05$) (Table 1). The phenolic compound exhibited the similar trend as that of DPPH. Total phenolic compound (TPC) increased with the increased concentration of fucoidan in FRE. The antioxidant activity of FRE exhibited the linear relationship $y = 13.46x - 11.61$; $R^2 = 0.99$ for this method (Fig 3).

Considering that the phenolic compounds are potent antioxidants in the plant extract, we studied the total phenolic content of the FRE. The highest level of total phenolic content was found with the highest concentration of fucoidan. Many studies have shown positive linear correlation between antioxidant capacity

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and total phenolic content of spices, medicinal herbs, and other dietary plants. Moreover, these results have also suggested that phenolic compounds are responsible for their antioxidant capacity (Cai *et al.*, 2004; Liu *et al.*, 2008; Shan *et al.*, 2005). The good TPC values of this FRE indicate their potential use as natural antioxidant ingredients to prevent oxidative rancidity and replace commonly used synthetic antioxidants such as butylatedhydroxytoluene (BHT) and butylatedhydroxyanisole (BHA) in animal feed (Singleton *et al.*, 1999) or may be synergistically added along with them.

Fig 3: Phenolic content of FRE with different concentration analysed using total phenolic assay

Antibacterial activity assay

The MIC values of FRE against the different bacterial strains were ranging from 62.5 μ l/ml to 125 μ l/ml (Table 2). The maximum activity was observed against *Aeromonas hydrophila* and *Staphylococcus aureus* with MIC value of 62.5 μ l/ml and least activity with MIC value 125 μ l/ml against *Micrococcus luteus*. The MBC values of FRE against the different bacterial strains were ranged from 125 μ l/ml to 250 μ l/ml (Table 2). The maximum activity was observed against *Staphylococcus aureus* with MBC value 125 μ l/ml.

The crude extracts of several algae were reported to inhibit only gram positive bacteria e.g. *P. gymnospora* and *Dictyotadichotoma* extracts while the *Hypnea musciformis* extracts showed activity against *Salmonella typhosa* ParaA (Rao & Parekh, 1981), *Sargassum uticum* extracts inhibited both of marine gram positive and negative bacteria (Hellio *et al.*, 2001). The specific substance in the extracts having antibacterial activity was not identified. In the present study, the FRE inhibited both gram positive (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Micrococcus luteus*) and negative bacteria (*Aeromonas hydrophila*). This is in agreement with Chotigeat *et al.* (2004), who reported that crude fucoidan extract inhibited both of gram negative (*V. harveyi* and *E. coli*) and gram positive bacteria (*S. aureus*) and was reported according to the concentration of fucoidan. The mechanism of fucoidan on antibacterial activity is required to be further studied.

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Table 2: Minimum inhibitory concentrations ($\mu\text{l/ml}$) and minimum bactericidal concentrations ($\mu\text{l/ml}$)* of FRE against fish and food borne pathogens

Bacteria	<i>Aeromona hydrophilla</i>		<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>		<i>Micrococcus luteus</i>	
	MIC ($\mu\text{l/ml}$)	MBC ($\mu\text{l/ml}$)	MIC ($\mu\text{l/ml}$)	MBC ($\mu\text{l/ml}$)	MIC ($\mu\text{l/ml}$)	MBC ($\mu\text{l/ml}$)
Fucoidan	62.5	250	62.5	125	125	250

Conversion: * 1000 $\mu\text{l/ml}$ = 110 mg/ml

CONCLUSION

It was observed that Indian brown seaweed contains about 5.5% fucoidan which is comparable with other potential source. The antioxidant activities and antibacterial activities were also high and equally comparable with other potential seaweed. Hence, fucoidan extract appears to be a potential nutraceutical and used as a crude form in animal feeds.

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